

Analyzing Case Study SMU816 (DBS: Digital Transformation to Best Bank in the World)

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3. Abbreviations (sorted alphabetically)

Abbreviation	Full Form
ADA	Advancing DBS with AI
BBIW	Best Bank in the World
BoD	Board of Directors
DBS	Development Bank of Singapore
DDD	Domain-Driven Design
DT	Digital Transformation
EA	Enterprise Architecture
ExO	Exponential Organization
GPUs	Graphical Process Units
HBS	Harvard Business School
KYC	Know Your Customer
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MTP	Massive Transformative Purpose
MVP	Minimum Viable Prototype
OKRs	Objectives and Key Results
PLC	Programmable Logic Controllers
ROE	Return on Equity
TWC	The Weather Company
VCs	Venture Capitalists

4. Executive Summary

This report provides an analysis of case study SMU816 which shows how DBS became BBIW using appropriate tools and examples to support the analysis.

5. Q1- Overview of DBS's DT to BBIW

5.1. Introduction

According to G. Westerman, MIT who defined digital transformation (DT) as a radical shift in thinking about how an organization uses technology, people, and processes to fundamentally change business performance; and considering Microsoft version of the definition: rethink how you bring people, data and processes together to create value for customers and maintain competitive advantage in a digital world, DBS applied a thorough understanding of DT by bringing together its EA capabilities into a digital culture that allowed it, not only reframing its competition dimensions, but also developing and running a scalable financial ecosystem across south Asia and accordingly become BBIW.

DBS competitive advantage came from end-to-end DT process (See below figure).

Figure 1: DT Process
Source: (Lamarre, et al., 2021)

5.2. DBS DT Strategy

Along strategy 1.0 (**Asia Bank of Choice**) 2010-2015, and with some helping factors: the relatively strong position after 2008 global financial crisis, the rise of FinTech and Alibaba in China, and its CEO technology background, DBS launched its DT journey ahead of many other banks carrying a tagline “living, breathing Aisa”. However, DBS recognized after its twelve-markets-presence (achieved via brick-and-mortar approach using different legacy systems), and along the failure to acquire Danamon bank (Indonesia) between 2012-2013 due to regulatory changes, recognized the need for strategy 2.0 (**Making Banking Joyful**) to be BBIW by 2020, thus, started with a new “sole” in 2014 carrying a “Live more, Bank less” tagline, and benefiting from its goldilocks size compared to larger legacy companies, towards shifting the whole organization culture via a customer-obsessed approach (Lamarre, et al., 2021). DBS developed a scalable digital platform that resulted in a collaborative ecosystem which enabled, in-turn, maximized value creation for the bank, the customer, the employees as well as society (*Figure 2*).

Source of Template : McKinsey & Company

Figure 2: DBS DT Dimensions
 Source: Author’s Finding

The bank achieved presence in eighteen markets (including Indonesia) and became not only the BBIW in 2018, but also an ExO which creates significant value via its digital strategy (*Figure 3*).

Figure 3: DBS Digital Strategy and its Main Initiatives
Source: SMU816

6. Q2- Enhancing Business Strategy through DT for Value Creation

Preface

Michael Boyles (HBS) explains how DT enhances the business strategy through the delivery of strategic initiatives a company pursues to create value for the organization and its stakeholders and gain a competitive advantage in the market.

“Companies that achieve enduring financial success create substantial value for their customers, their employees, or their suppliers” (Oberholzer-Gee, 2021).

6.1. Value Stick Framework

Using the value stick framework (*Figure 4*), firms can increase their margins by either creating more value to their customers to pay more, or, by making it is more attractive for potential talent to join the firm at lower salaries, as well as by making it easier and more worthy for suppliers to partner with the firm at lower prices (Oberholzer-Gee, 2021).

Willingness- to- pay (WTP) sits at the top end of the value stick. It represents the customer’s point of view. More specifically, it is the most a customer would ever pay for a product or service. If companies find ways to improve their product, WTP will increase.

Willingness- to- sell (WTS), at the bottom end of the value stick, refers to employees and suppliers. For employees, it is the minimum compensation they require to accept a job offer. If companies make work more attractive, WTS declines. For suppliers, it is the lowest price at which they are willing to sell products and services. If companies make it easier for their suppliers to produce and ship products, supplier WTS will fall.

Figure 4: Value Stick Framework
Source: Author’s Finding

Best Buy, for instance, has applied the value stick theory (*Figure 5*) after having recorded \$1.7 billion lose in 2012. It was unable, even with its widely available showrooms, to tackle the growing e-commerce trend. Customers used to visit its stores to decide which products they like and then buy them online from Amazon. Best Buy innovated with the store-in-store mechanism and created value for customers, suppliers, and employees. It shipped from 400 stores in 2013 and achieved a 3.5X shipping-point increase in a year; breaking Amazon’s delivery Leadtime. Additionally, Best Buy improved its website, and in few years later, its online sales boomed, and Best Buy website competed leading e-commerce sites (Oberholzer-Gee, 2021).

Figure 5: Best Buy Value Stick Simulation
Source: Author's Finding

The DBS case study has provided evidence of applying the value stick theory (*Figure 6*) through DT whereas the bank was able to prove digital value capture by growing its 33% digital-customer base in 2015 to be 48% in 2018 (and 62% in 2023) having 20% lower cost-to-income ratio with each digital customer compared to traditional customer. The revenue per digital customer was double the revenue of a traditional customer. There were also substantial cost savings from servicing a digitally active customer who did not need a relationship manager or paper forms to transact (SMU816, 2020).

Figure 6: DBS Value Stick Simulation
Source: Author's Finding

Many customer delighters (*Figure 7*) made by DBS's DT and increased the margin through transforming traditional customer to be digitally active.

Figure 7: Delighters made to DBS's customers via DT
Source: Author's Finding

6.2. The Five-Key Domains of Digital Strategy

David Rogers explains that 70% of digital transformations fail, whereby the remaining share a common approach which leverages rethinking of five elements: customers, competition, data, innovation and value (Rogers, 2023). DT is a journey (not a project) that requires adaptation of five strategy domains associated with above-mentioned elements (**Figure 8**) with a wide involvement of all functions across all organizational levels and through an agile management that promotes experimentation over extensive planning, allows quick-and-cheap failures, and leverages bottom-up data-driven evolving decision-making rather than top-down very cautious governance (Rogers, 2016).

Domains	Strategic themes	Key concepts
 Customers	<i>Harness customer networks</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reinvented marketing funnel • path to purchase • core behaviors of customer networks
 Competition	<i>Build platforms, not just products</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • platform business models • (in)direct network effects • (dis)intermediation • competitive value trains
 Data	<i>Turn data into assets</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • templates of data value • drivers of big data • data-driven decision making
 Innovation	<i>Innovate by rapid experimentation</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • divergent experimentation • convergent experimentation • minimum viable prototype • paths to scaling up
 Value	<i>Adapt your value proposition</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • concepts of market value • paths out of a declining market • steps to value prop evolution

Figure 8: The Five-Key Domains of Digital Strategy
 Source: (Rogers, 2016)

DBS applied the five DT domains theory. Here below are examples showing how successfully transforming firms were adopting each of these domains and how DBS was also doing in the same regard.

6.2.1. Re-Thinking Customer

Figure 9: Firms harnessing customer network to grow
Source: Author's Finding

Figure 10: DBS harnessing customer network to grow
Source: SMU816

6.2.2. Re-Thinking Competition

Figure 11: Firms building platforms, not just products, to grow
Source: Author's Finding

Figure 12: DBS building a platform, not just products, to grow
Source: SMU816

6.2.3. Re-Thinking Data

Figure 13: Firms turning data into asset, to grow
Source: Author's Finding

Figure 14: DBS turning data into asset, to grow
Source: SMU816

6.2.4. Re-Thinking Innovation

Figure 15: Firms innovating by rapid experimentation, to grow
Source: Author's Finding

Figure 16: DBS innovating by rapid experimentation, to grow
Source: SMU816

6.2.5. Re-Thinking Value

Figure 17: Firms adapting their value proposition, to grow
Source: Author's Finding

Figure 18; DBS adapting its value proposition, to grow
Source: SMU816

7. Q3- DBS's Journey to Becoming an Exponential Organization

7.1. Overview of ExO

The definition of ExO has evolved throughout the digital age (**Figure 19**) due to the fact that ExO usually finds ways of radically dropping the marginal cost of supply through the growing application of Peter's Six Ds to computing: Digitalization, Deception, Disruption, Demonetization, Dematerialization Democratization (Ismail, et al., 2023).

Figure 19: ExO Definition 2014 to 2023
Source: Author's Finding

ExO carries ten common attributes that allow it to pursue an MTP which, in turn, establishes a long-term goal for the whole company so sweeping and profound that it is always within reach yet always unreachable (**Figure 20**).

Figure 20: MTP Attributes
Source: (Ismail, et al., 2023)

7.2. DBS MTP

DBS DT enabled it, over a decade, to achieve multiple scores of KPIs (DBS, 2023). It achieved 1.5X growth in the digital share of customers since 2017, and 3X growth of digital customer income (Figure 21). DBS achieved, in 2018, \$154,167 profit-per-employee (SMU816, 2020) which was within the top 100 globally, and equal to 40% of Apple's rate, 52% of Google's, and 57% of Microsoft's (Tibalti, 2020).

Figure 21: DBS Progress with Digital Customers
Source: DBS Annual Report 2023

Additionally, DBS as an ExO, has an ROE which goes far beyond its peers in Singapore (Figure 22)

Figure 22: DBS ROE Over Years
Source: DBS Annual Report 2023

To analyze DBS MTP, ExO characteristics will be explained, one by one, with examples of relevant DBS practices that demonstrate the theory dimensions.

7.2.1. SCALE: Outward-Facing Characteristics

7.2.1.1. Staff on Demand

It is about increasing speed and functionality by leveraging external workers according to need rather than hiring internal employees (Figure 23).

Erwin Chong, Group Head of Corporate Real Estate at DBS says, Since January 2021, DBS has adopted a permanent hybrid workforce model, with all employees given the flexibility to work remotely up to 40% of the time. The bank further found that with employee life cycles being increasingly dynamic, work arrangements needed to become more flexible to support different needs, and subsequently became among the first Singapore companies to roll out a formal job-sharing scheme. This enables two employees to share the responsibilities of one full-time role, while retaining all existing medical benefits in full and covered under the bank's insurance plans.

Hybrid Workforce Model

Figure 23: DBS as an ExO - Staff on Demand
Source: DBS Annual Report 2023

7.2.1.2. Community and Crowd

It is about attracting, engaging, and leveraging communities and the crowd, whose like-mindedness adds to creativity, validation, and even funding efforts (**Figure 24**).

- In 2016, Sparks was watched by more than 250 million viewers by 2018.
- DBS has 10 million retail customers in 2019 and 17.9 in 2023.
- DBS Engaged in more than 200,000 hours of employee volunteerism activities during 2023.
- DBS reached out to 59,000 participants via some 400 digital and financial literacy workshops or initiatives.

Social Media and volunteerism activities

Figure 24: DBS as an ExO - Community and Crowd
Source: SMU816 and DBS Annual Report 2023

7.2.1.3. AI & Algorithms

It is about Leveraging automated functions (machine learning, deep learning, etc.) to obtain new insights and automate operations and services. (**Figure 25**).

- DigiBank Customer service was done through artificial intelligence (AI) virtual assistants or chatbots that were trained to answer the most common questions.
- Since 2016, DBS audit team began to periodically analyze 100% of the available data it had, rather than performing random sampling using a traditional cycle-based approach. It built the capability to extract this data itself, instead of waiting for the business to provide it. It moved from a deductive approach to a predictive one, such as using machine learning to audit bank branches to detect patterns and identify which branches were at higher risk, and allocating more audit resources to those branches
- In June 2018, Human Resources adopted the use of AI for recruitment—Southeast Asia’s first virtual bank recruiter, “Jim” (short for Jobs Intelligence Maestro), was born as a result of the collaboration between the talent acquisition team and an AI start-up.
- DBS continued to leverage data analytics and artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ ML) to deepen the engagement with customers. In 2023, DBS engaged 8.6 million customers across the region via personalized nudges, guiding them towards better investment and financial planning decisions.

AI virtual Assistants, Audit Patterns, Jim, and Personalized Nudges

Figure 25: DBS as an ExO – AI & Algorithms
Source: SMU816 and DBS Annual Report 2023

7.2.1.4. Leveraged Assets

It is about accessing, sharing, renting, or otherwise outsourcing assets to remain nimble and reduce capital expenditures (**Figure 26**).

- The API ecosystem that the bank was developing provided a solution for paperless KYC by allowing it to partner with Café Coffee Day, a local coffee chain with about 600 outlets throughout India.
- In November 2018, DBS launched DigiBank Indonesia, announcing local ride-hailing service GO-JEK as its ecosystem partner

API Ecosystem Instead of Physical Branches

Figure 26: DBS as an ExO – Leveraged Assets
Source: SMU816

7.2.1.5. Engagement

It is about leveraging outside interest through gamification, digital reputation systems, incentive programs, and crypto economics to create network effects and positive feedback loops (**Figure 27**).

- POSB Smart Buddy Program made good progress in extending the world's first integrated in-school savings and payments program to more schools. POSB, which was launched in 2017, creates a contactless payments ecosystem within the school environment to help cultivate sensible savings and spending habits among young students in an interactive, engaging manner. These students are then better equipped to achieve financial wellness when they transition to the next stage of their lives.
- DBS signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Ministry of Education (MOE) to install a digital payment infrastructure in more than 330 primary and secondary schools, junior colleges/ Millennia Institute, and special education (SPED) schools by 2025. Under the partnership, DBS will also provide up to 400,000 students with smartwatches and cards for payments.
- DBS stepped up its digital literacy programs for seniors in the community. It extended these programs to hawker centers and also created a new anti-scam and cybersecurity quiz that was codeveloped with the Cyber Security Agency of Singapore and IMDA.

POSB, Partnership with MoE, Partnership with Technology Organizations

Figure 27: DBS as an ExO – Engagement
Source: DBS Annual Report 2023

7.2.2. IDEAS: Inward-Facing Characteristics

7.2.2.1. Interfaces

It is about having diverse ways of interacting, processing, and automating the SCALE attributes so the organization is doing the right work at the right time.

DBS interfaced its customer through multiple channels like but not limited to PayLah, Sparks, DigiBank, iWealth, Prism, and POSB (SMU816, 2020).

7.2.2.2. Dashboards

It is about making real-time information, with essential company and employee metrics based on OKRs, accessible to everyone internally, with short feedback loops (**Figure 28**).

-
- DBS has hardcore data scientists, who in many cases are hired. Then there's a whole community of data translators, who are mostly existing staff. They're people who understand the business and business analytics, who can be a bridge between the data modelling and everything else.
 - DBS dashboards allow users to see if the transformation is on track
 - DBS also shares the balanced scorecard in the annual report.

Data Translators, Traceability, and Transparency

Figure 28: DBS as an ExO – Dashboards
Source: SMU816

7.2.2.3. Experimentation

It is about introducing lean startup methodology in all departments, with new ideas and processes, culturally enabling rapid, validated learning. (**Figure 29**).

-
- DBS leveraged 'Culture by Design' to identify the new desired culture, and what had to be done to transform the culture.
 - Start-up culture including: be agile, be a learning Org, be customer obsessed, be data-driven, and be experiment and risk taking
 - DBS didn't only give positive recognition to early successes, but even created a 'Dare to Fail award' for those who tried something new and failed, thus giving the signal that it was okay to do so.

Culture by Design, ABCDE, and Recognition of Experimenters

Figure 29: DBS as an ExO – Experimentation
Source: SMU816

7.2.2.4. Autonomy

It is about instituting a flat structure that allows individual employees or multidisciplinary teams to operate independently and effectively (**Figure 30**).

In 2017, HR introduced DigiFY, a mobile and online platform aimed at providing fundamental digital training to DBS's bankers to transform them into 'digital bankers'. After completing the training in the seven areas of agility, data-driven mindset, digital business models, digital communications, digital technologies, journey thinking, and risk and controls, bankers would be certified and equipped to pass on the knowledge to their colleagues

DBS Digital Bankers

Figure 30: DBS as an ExO – Autonomy
Source: SMU816

7.2.2.5. Social Technologies

It is about leveraging peer-to-peer collaborative tools to facilitate transparent, real-time conversations across the organization (**Figure 31**).

- Different methods were implemented by DBS to support employee's transformation as the bank became a learning organization, such as eliminating approval for any skills training course less than S\$500.
- "ITQ" (I Thank You) was launched in 2017, an online peer-to-peer recognition program that made saying thank you to anyone across the bank (and across geographies) straightforward.
- Leaders had a reverse mentor to provide opportunities to learn areas of the business in a one-on-one meeting with an employee. This also allowed them to probe and ask questions that they may not ask in meetings or other situations

DBS Employees Knowledge Transfer and Collaboration

Figure 31: DBS as an ExO – Social Technologies
Source: SMU816

8. Q4- Integration of Digital Strategy with Business Strategy

Preface

In a digital era, it is flawed assumption to imagine a bank will continue operate traditionally and that fintech giants will not disrupt it. Alibaba, for instance, with its digital repository for consumers' leftover cash from online spending, has become the world's largest money-market fund, with \$165.6 billion under management, overtaking JPMorgan's \$150 billion money market fund To successfully transform, Digital leaders can't just create a separate digital arm, or run experiments, or use technology to improve efficiency. However, they must craft a digital strategy as an integral part of their business strategy (Gupta, 2018). *These thoughts have been realized so early by Piyush Gupta, CEO of DBS, who was able to see what they were being able to do in China.*

Digital strategy is defined as the process of specifying an organization's vision, goals, opportunities, and related activities to maximize the business benefits of digital initiatives to the organization (Westerman, et al., 2014).

This can be achieved using a framework of twelve steps (**Figure 32**).

Figure 32: Driving Digital Strategy Framework
Source: (Gupta, 2018)

The following sub-paragraphs elaborate on each of the framework steps giving known real-word examples and explain how DBS has achieved that.

8.1. Reimagine Your Business

8.1.1. Business scope

Digitalization changes the core business scope. Transforming companies shall carefully balance broadening the new digital scope while carrying core competencies (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Amazon started as an online bookstore, then became an e-commerce giant and logistics' market leader, and later, a cloud technology leader.</p>	<p>DBS, using a joyful question: "what could Jeff do?" reimagined its banking scope into an open e-commerce platform which resulted in an API-powered platform with 450 API in 2019. Accordingly, DBS became an e-banking technology integrator.</p>

Table 1: Examples of Reimagine Your Business Scope - Source: Author's Finding

8.1.2. Business Model

Digitalization requires rethinking the business model considering the continuous change of competition rules. Shifting into a platform is a key success factor (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>NYT, believing that end users still cared about reliable journalism of high quality, rather than public tweets or free web blogs' information, shifted into a subscription-based e-news platform.</p>	<p>DBS, through DigiBank, brought together an entire suite of ground-breaking technology – from biometrics to artificial intelligence (AI) – to enable customers to enjoy a whole new way of banking. Breaking away from conventional banking norms with their onerous form-filling and cumbersome processes.</p>

Table 2: Examples of Reimagine Your Business Model - Source: Author's Finding

8.1.3. Platforms and Ecosystems

Platform and ecosystems transform industries through connecting multiple parties, such as buyers and sellers, or consumers and developers, which dramatically reduce the cost of supply (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>GE decided to open its Predix platform to non-GE customers shifting it into the first platform for industrial products that leverage big data analytics for better productivity, not limited to optimizing individual turbines but warranting a farm-level optimization.</p>	<p>DBS published a research paper titled “Pivot or Perish: Ecosystem, the emerging business model.” It defined an ecosystem as “Bringing together entities in disparate industries to create new offerings or capture value that individual companies or sectors may not be capable of creating on their own. Through ecosystems, marketers gain the ability to cater to customer needs, without prompting the customer to look further than the company for a product.</p>

Table 3: Examples of Platforms and Ecosystems - Source: Author’s Finding

8.2. Reevaluate Your Value Chain

8.2.1. Rethinking R&D and Innovation

Leveraging the expertise and insights of both users and experts outside the company, often called open innovation or crowdsourcing, has been on the rise in recent years. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>In 2013, NASA held a public contest with Harvard University, offering a \$30,000 prize for solving a coding problem. Believing that the public might outperform their scientists, NASA received 2,185 entries, half of which were better than their internal solutions, with one entry winning the prize.</p>	<p>In DBS, and from 2015, hackathons were organized where employees would join with external coders and entrepreneurs (from start-ups) to form a team of about ten people, for a three-day design session, which was preceded by two-days of education and problem identification. Each team had 72 hours to solve a problem through customer interviews, focus groups, and storyboarding, the objective was to create an App which the team had to showcase on the fifth last day.</p>

Table 4: Examples of Rethinking R&D and Innovation - Source: Author’s Finding

8.2.2. Operational Excellence

It is essential to distinguish DT from automation. A digital factory, by comparison, provides all the advantages of automation in terms of speed and efficiency but also allows for flexibility and tracking. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Siemens developed a smart factory, in Amberg, that produces industrial PLCs, devices. Almost 75% of operations in that factory are digitized and fully-automated.</p>	<p>In June 2018, DBS's HR adopted AI for recruitment, introducing "Jim," a virtual recruiter that automated pre-screening, saving time and allowing recruiters to focus on sourcing and interviews. Jim's 24/7 availability improved real-time interactions and psychometric assessments, leading to better hires, and reduced turnover rates.</p>

Table 5: Examples of Operational Excellence - Source: Author's Finding

8.2.3. Omnichannel Strategy

Online banking transactions may indeed replace a large volume of physical operation. Companies managing this challenging transition build the online channel without jeopardizing the offline channel keeping different channels as complements, not as competing substitutes. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Finansbank, in Türkiye, initially focused on wholesale commercial banking. It expanded later into retail banking, targeting the mass segment with credit cards and consumer loans. By 2010, it started serving the fast-growing middle-income private banking segment, which had been ignored earlier.</p>	<p>In addition to its retail banking and SME (small medium Enterprises), DBS rolled out in 2017 its iWealth, an app for its priority and private banking clients. iWealth would enable private banking clients to access their investment portfolios immediately and customize reporting according to their preferences, such as by asset type or currency. In 2018, the Wealth business division's income grew by 26%. iWealth, accordingly, leveraged a successful implementation of the DBS omnichannel strategy.</p>

Table 6: Examples of Omnichannel Strategy - Source: Author's Finding

8.3. Reconnect with Your Customers

8.3.1. Acquiring Customers

Acquiring new customers is a major driver of growth. However, customer acquiring costs vary widely, thus, companies shall deeply analyze customer segments and find the best-fit acquiring ways for the most profitable future (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p data-bbox="285 863 399 894">Sapphire</p> <p data-bbox="505 604 837 978">In 2016, Chase launched its Sapphire Card with a highly attractive offer, including valuable gifts. Despite a \$450 annual fee, the card's popularity was so high that Chase ran out of the metal used to make it within a month, surpassing their annual customer target in under two weeks.</p>	<p data-bbox="862 604 1424 978">DBS had hypothesized that digitally active customers would cost 20% less than non-digital customers. The bank termed this positive outcome 'digital value capture'. DBS then began to track these two groups of customers, and the activities they undertook separately. DBS encouraged customers through incentives to use its digital services. In 2018, 48% of DBS customers became digital. In 2023, the percent reached 62% with 3X better cost-to-income ratio.</p>

Table 7: Examples of Acquiring Customers - Source: Author's Finding

8.3.2. Engaging Consumers

The goal of marketing is “the right message, to the right customer, at the right time”. Almost 84% of millennials admit to skipping or blocking ADs. Advertising shall provide value to consumers by offering relevant information that enables better decisions. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p data-bbox="505 1480 837 1785">In 2014, Hindustan Unilever launched Kan Khajura entertainment service via basic mobile phones. Users enjoyed 15 minutes of fun and ADs via toll-free calls. The channel shortly grew to engage 35 million users boosting the brand.</p>	<p data-bbox="862 1480 1424 1785">To better engage customers digitally, DBS improved the user experience for its retail and institutional digital platforms using purposely-designed social media. In 2016, DBS launched Sparks videos which have been watched by more than 250 million viewers by 2018 and played a significant part in triggering about 10% of the customer inquiries that the bank further received.</p>

Table 8: Examples of Engaging Customers - Source: Author's Finding

8.3.3. Measuring and Optimizing Marketing Spend

Big data has allowed executives to easily find patterns and correlations in the digital era. Correlation might really be an enabler for the data to “speak” for itself. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>In 2011, Starbucks fans, and their friends, spent 8% more and transacted 11% more frequently than the average internet user who usually transacted at Starbucks.</p>	<p>DBS set a strict criterion to track how much it was converting traditional customers to digital. Digital customers were requalified on a rolling 12-months basis. DBS EATE measures enabled, via dashboards, data visualization so that DBS users could see if the transformation was on track.</p>

Table 9: Examples of Measuring and Optimizing Marketing Spend - Source: Author's Finding

8.4. Rebuild Your Organization

8.4.1. Managing Digital Transition

Implementing change in large organizations is highly challenging. Unlike startups, legacy companies shall balance leveraging existing assets with the need to innovate. Companies must create a vision and a transformation roadmap. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Adobe re-built its Org. capabilities through digital marketing and data, leading to its acquisition of Omniture, a digital marketing firm. This strategic move transformed Adobe, with digital content marketing contributing 30% of its total revenue by 2016.</p>	<p>To fully embrace digital transformation, DBS overhauled its core legacy systems noting that many others would doubt the feasibility of such a substantial change. However, DBS leveraged its unique position, finding that its "Goldilocks" size allowed it to tackle this mission more effectively than larger organizations might. This approach proved not only feasible but also highly compelling and productive, as they committed to a complete and aggressive transformation.</p>

Table 10: Examples of Managing Digital Transition - Source: Author's Finding

8.4.2. Designing the Organization for Innovation

To achieve a successful transformation, organizational culture must shift to become customer-obsessed. It is essential that everyone in the organization is fully aligned with the vision, strategy, and strategic priorities. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Mastercard transformed its innovation culture by integrating startups into its operations, creating a "landing dock" for collaboration. It made aligned its innovation with strategic priorities, focusing on its core business, geographic expansion, and new ventures, all guided by industry principles, global regulations, collaboration, and cybersecurity.</p>	<p>DBS created a data-first culture by changing employees' mindsets and work processes. DBS digital strategy focused on four components: 1) fostering a culture of data-driven decision-making, 2) building capabilities across the whole bank at all levels and within all its functions (including corporate ones like Audit), 3) ensuring data protection (via PURE committee) while making it accessible and usable, and 4) developing future-proof infrastructure with advanced AI, ML, GPUs and big data analytics.</p>

Table 11: Examples of Designing the Organization for Innovation - Source: Author's Finding

8.4.3. Skills, Capability, and Talent Management

AI will impact future work and skills. Companies need special expertise to perform big-data analytics. It is crucial for companies to re-skill/up-skill their talent for more powerful digital capabilities. (Gupta, 2018). See below table.

Real-word Successful example	Example of DBS Act
<p>Google, as a learning organization, leveraged its talent capabilities into machine learning. Accordingly, Google Translate, for instance, became so accurate that it is hard to distinguish its translations from those done by a linguist. It can now automatically translate conversations in real time.</p>	<p>DBS started hiring data scientists and reskilling business analysts who understand business and business analytics and can play a bridge role between the data modelling and everything else. DBS achieved early successes, such as predicting when a salesperson would leave the bank, and when customer calls might be received. Additionally, in 2017, DBS HR introduced DigiFY, to transform all employees into 'digital bankers'.</p>

Table 12: Examples of Skills, Capability, and Talent Management - Source: Author's Finding

9. Q5- Integration of Phases of DT and Leadership Management

Preface

Success in the digital era demands that organizations deeply embed digital capabilities into their core, ensuring innovation becomes a discipline to "becoming digital" (perpetual transformation) rather than "doing digital" (a one-time transformation). Such a disciplined approach is essential for both taking off (initial success) and staying ahead (ongoing success) in digital transformation.

Five maturity stages of digital transformation (**Figure 33**) have been recognized globally, each has different challenges and common possible failure reasons, thus, companies shall make sure applying the above-mentioned discipline approach (Saldanha, 2019).

Figure 33: Five stages of digital transformation
Source: (Saldanha, 2019)

9.1. Stage 1 – Foundation

In this stage companies involve automating internal processes to enhance efficiency. However, failure may occur if teams lose focus on the intended business value or execute poorly. To mitigate these risks, committed ownership at the highest levels and iterative execution are essential (Saldanha, 2019).

The initial HealthCare.gov website traffic on the exchange was higher than expected. Its crash provided an important lesson on breaking up large “waterfall” projects into smaller iterative ones (Saldanha, 2019).

DBS passed this stage in 2008. See below figure.

In 2008, DBS encountered a delayed technology project lacking clear goals and running at \$73 million extra cost on top of its original \$147 million budget. They cancelled the ambitious project and later recognized the failure as a valuable lesson (down-payment) contributing to the transformation journey.

Dave cancelled the endless project

Figure 34: DBS DT Stage 1 – Foundation
Source: SMU816

9.2. Stage 2 – Solid

In this stage major digital processes and/or products start developing organically in parts of the organization. Failure comes from underpowering change leaders and poor transformation choices.

DBS passed this stage around 2014. See below figure.

DBS mitigated this risk through eliminating steering committees and delegating the technology team to run projects with clear context and traceable outcome of customer growth, deeper market penetration and new digital services.

DBS Eliminated Steering committees

Figure 35: DBS DT Stage 2 – Solid
Source: SMU816

9.3. Stage 3 – Partially Synchronized

In this stage, companies achieve partial completion of an enterprise-wide strategy. Failure comes from ineffective change management and insufficient transformation strategy (Saldanha, 2019).

P&G's integration of Gillette offers key lessons in successful change management. Despite the high failure rate of mergers, P&G achieved success by prioritizing integration, handpicking dedicated teams, aligning IT strategies quickly, and establishing clear decision-making structures. The disciplined execution made that integration a best-in-class success, delivering over \$1 billion annual cost synergies (Saldanha, 2019).

DBS passed this stage around 2018. See below figure.

DBS transformed its approach by reorganizing teams to align business and technology goals, adopting platform thinking, and establishing shared KPIs. The mantra “business equals technology; technology equals business” was embraced, fostering collaboration between tech and business leaders through the "Two in a Box" model. DevOps principles and automation were introduced to enable faster product rollouts and quick responses to customer feedback, leading to rapid learning and continuous improvement. This holistic approach ensured that business and technology worked seamlessly together to drive sustained success

DBS Leveraged Two in a Box model

Figure 36: DBS DT Stage 3 – Partially Synchronized
Source: SMU816

DBS passed DT stage-3 into stage-4 between 2018 and 2019 with its Ecosystem (Speculand, 2019). See below table.

Year	DBS Successful Launch
2014	DBS Digital Wallet (PayLah)
2016	Sparks Movie Series and DigiBank India
2017	iWealth, DBS Platform with 200 APIs and 80 Partners, Prism, DigiFY, and iTQ
2018	BOSB, Jim and DigiBank Indonesia
2019	DBS Platform with 450 APIs and DBS Ecosystem (Pivot or Perish)

Table 13: DBS Successful Launches 2014 to 2019

9.4. Stage 4 – Fully Synchronized

This stage marks the full implementation of an enterprise-wide digital platform or business model. However, it remains vulnerable to disruption without ongoing adaptation. Success requires digital reorganization and staying updated on technological advancements. Organizational structure and digital literacy are critical risk factors at this stage.

DBS early recognized a 'Dare to Fail' award, and enabled risk-takers. It stayed current on technology, in a comparable way that is described by the five-stages theory.

Below table shows the evidence:

DT 5-Stages Theory – Stay Current Discipline	Example of DBS Act
Creating executive learning opportunities	DBS leaders had a reverse mentor to provide opportunities to learn areas of the business in a one-on-one meeting with an employee. This also allowed them to probe and ask questions that they may not ask in meetings or other situations. (SMU816, 2020).
Partnering with VCs and start-ups	In January 2019, DBS released a research paper titled "Pivot or Perish: Ecosystem, the Emerging Business Model,". (SMU816, 2020).
Leveraging partners for education	DBS signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Ministry of Education (MOE) to install a digital payment infrastructure in more than 330 primary and secondary schools, junior colleges/ Millennia Institute, and special education (SPED) schools by 2025. Under the partnership, DBS will also provide up to 400,000 students with smartwatches and cards for payments (DBS, 2023).
Opening up your data via APIs to others	In November 2017, DBS launched the world's largest banking API platform. The platform went live with more than 200 APIs and more than 80 DBS partners, ranging from Fintech start-ups to telcos. The use of APIs enabled the bank to integrate external partners seamlessly into its digital ecosystem, to create new customer applications and scale its range of new product and service offerings easily. In 2018, DBS launched different Marketplaces for cars, property, and electricity, providing a reliable source of such listings to its customers. As at August 2019, DBS had over 450 APIs (SMU816, 2020).
Enlisting the help of digital ambassadors	DBS BoD consists of 6 independent directors out of 10 members. The Lead Independent Director, Mr. Olivier Lim, has regular private sessions with the other independent Directors in the course of the year and provides feedback to the Chairman where necessary (DBS, 2023).

Table 14: DT Five Stages Theory – DBS Stay Current Discipline

9.5. Stage 5 – Living DNA

This stage represents the phase of perpetual transformation, where the transforming company achieves an agile culture and becomes a market leader. This stage requires maintaining the digital culture and regularly sensing disruption risks.

DBS is nowadays at stage 5 (DBS, 2023). See below figure.

Building a Sustainable Advantage

DBS, as of today, carries a new tagline “**building a sustainable advantage**”. This can be perceived from the chairman and CEO letter: The challenges facing our world – from military conflicts to rapid technological change to the present climate crisis – are multifaceted and complex. To future-proof ourselves, we need to strengthen our existing competencies and invest in new capabilities, while being nimble enough to respond to any unexpected changes in the external environment. As we have done in the past, we will continue to build on our DNA as an innovation-led, purpose-driven bank to build a sustainable advantage

DBS is Moving From making Banking Joyful to Building a Sustainable Advantage

Figure 37: DBS DT Stage 5 – Digital Living DNA
Source: DBS Annual Report 2023

10. References

- Anon., 2021. *InfoSys - DBS GETTING READY TO CONQUER ASIA'S WEALTH*. [Online] Available at: https://www.edgeverve.com/finacle/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/DBS_for_Wealth_Management.pdf [Accessed 31 08 2024].
- Birch, K., 2022. *Singapore's DBS Bank is reinventing workplace culture*. [Online] Available at: <https://businesschief.asia/leadership-and-strategy/singapore-dbs-bank-reinventing-workplace-culture> [Accessed 27 8 2024].
- Choo, S. S. & Henderson, J., 2019. *How DBS became the 'world's best bank' through digital transformation* [Interview] (26 8 2019).
- DBS, 2014. *Annual Report*, s.l.: DBS Group Holdings Ltd.
- DBS, 2015. *Annual Reprot*, s.l.: DBS Group Holdings Ltd.
- DBS, 2023. *Annual Report*, s.l.: DBS Group Holdings Ltd.
- Fenton, A., Fletcher, G. & Griffiths, M., 2020. *Strategic Digital Transformation: A Results- Driven Approach*. s.l.:Routledge.
- Gledhill, D. & HV, V., 2018. *Transforming a bank by becoming digital to the core* [Interview] 2018.
- Gupta, S., 2018. *Driving Digital Strategy - A Guide to Reimagining Your Business*. s.l.:Harvard Business Review Press.
- Ismail, S., Diamandis, P. H. & Malone, M. S., 2023. *Exponential Organizations 2.0*. 1 ed. s.l.:Ethos Collective.
- Lamarre, E., Smaje, K. & Zimmel, D., 2021. *Rewired: The McKinsey Guide to Outcompeting in the Age of Digital and AI*. s.l.:Wiley.
- Ng, J. & Anjum, Z., 2021. *How DBS Bank's digitalisation paid off during the pandemic* [Interview] (2 5 2021).
- Oberholzer-Gee, F., 2021. *Better, Simpler Strategy*. s.l.:Harvard Business School Publishing Corporation.
- Parashar, M., 2023. *Transforming DBS PayLah! with Domain-Driven Design*. [Online] Available at: <https://medium.com/dbs-tech-blog/transforming-dbs-paylah-with-domain-driven-design-bfd5ebfaefc9> [Accessed 28 8 2024].
- Rogers, D., 2016. *The Digital Transformation Playbook*. s.l.:Columbia University Press.
- Rogers, D., 2023. *The Digital Transformation Roadmap: Overcoming Barriers for Tech Success*. [Online]

Available at: <https://youtu.be/Fbq14Mi5JtU>
[Accessed 26 08 2023].

Saldanha, T., 2019. *Why Digital Transformations Fail*. s.l.:BK.

SMU816 (2020) SMU.

Sok Hui, C. & Sengupta, J., 2020. *McKensy&Company - Becoming more than a bank: Digital transformation at DBS* [Interview] (9 1 2020).

Speculand, R., 2019. *Transformation to the Best Digital / Bank in the World*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.bridgesconsultancy.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/DBS-Bank-Transformation-to-Best-Digital-and-Bank-in-the-World.pdf>
[Accessed 27 08 2024].

Tibalti, 2020. *Profit per Employee*. [Online]
Available at: <https://tipalti.com/profit-per-employee/>
[Accessed 30 8 2024].

Westerman, G., Bonnet, D. & McAfee, A., 2014. *Leading Digital - Turning Technology Into Business Transformation*. s.l.:Harvard Business Review Press.